

Study of folklores and cultural uses of mammals and anthropogenic impacts on diversity and distribution of mammals-a review

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SUMMARY

Humans and animals are directly or indirectly related to each others in order to fulfill their needs. History reveals the record of animals used by the humans for different purposes, such as food, medicines, games, commercial, traditional and magical uses. Mammalian species have different preferences as some of them like to accommodate areas which are near to human being, while some species of mammals feel shy to crowd areas and like to live in natural areas. Anthropogenic effects highly influenced the species of mammals. Some mammalian species have adaptations to adjust in the environment but other become extinct and rare. Continuous increase in populace of humans is cause of threat to the mammalian diversity. Human activities such as urbanization and agricultural uses forces mammals for migration. Change in temperature, reduction in precipitation and human activities cause extinction of mammals. Mammals have their importance in conservation of nature. As there is umbrella specie which possesses comparatively home rage at large scale, protect habitat for populace and help in protecting habitats for other species. Mammals considered important as they help in pollination and play role in environmental indication. IUCN plays important role in conservation of threatened species. Zootherapy is a kind of therapy in which animals and their body derived products are used to make medicines for treating illness of humans. Domestic and wild mammals and their body derived products are used in traditional medicines but these animals also have their importance as raw material in making herbal and modern medicines. Even a single disease is cured by many species of animals. it indicates effectiveness of zootherapeutic treatment. This investigation was organized to get knowledge about diversity of mammals of cities, villages, forests and agricultural lands present in Uchali complex. This study also has importance because people of that area are able to know that how their activities have harmful effects on mammalian diversity. Uses of mammals in different field have found out, which are beneficial for humans of Uchali complex.

Key words: Mammals, Anthropogenic effect, Pollination, Zootherapeutic treatment, Uchali complex

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INTRODUCTION

ETHNOZOOLOGY

The study of connection between humans and animals resources surrounding them takes place under ethnozoology (Lohani *et al.*, 2008; Saleem *et al.*, 2021; Umair *et al.*, 2022). It is documented for warm blooded animals (mammals); the relationship of more specie fullness with area having multiplex geography is recorded. Wide analyses were done on biogeography of mammals in North America which show slack and long slope in different solidity of species. The longitudinal slope follows topographic complicacy (Simpson, 1964). Ethno-mammalogy is knowledge about mammalian species. It is study of traditional use of mammals for betterment of humans (Alves and Rosa, 2007). Nobody can deny the important role of mammalian species in human's life (Alves *et al.*, 2009; Ijaz *et al.*, 2020). Mammals show environmental, social, religious, practical, therapeutic or nourishing importance; also increasing values for mammalian species in this world results in increase of mammalian trade. Increase in trading is major driver of mammalian extinction Mammals are solded in markets and it provide important information about local fauna (Alves *et al.*, 2012).

Ethno-mammalogy is the investigations of people, knowledge about warm blooded animals (mammals); ethno-mammalogy is area of investigation which provide help to increase protection effort, because it will boost the process of getting awareness related to natural variety (Alves and Souto, 2015). Information about the native persons and variety present in cities and rural-urban transition zone are necessary to surveyed because there is need to preserve mammalian species. In any case, this examination (Roberts, 2005a, b) is ignored or some investigators emphasized on the perspective throughout study in Pakistan (Altaf, 2016; Altaf, 2017; Altaf *et al.*, 2017; Altaf, 2018; Altaf *et al.*, 2018; Kanwal *et al.*, 2019; Afsheen *et al.*, 2020; Aslam and Faiz, 2020; Ijaz *et al.*, 2020; Abbasi, 2021; Riaz and Altaf, 2021).

HABITAT PREFERENCES OF MAMMALS

Mammalian species have choice of choosing habitat. Some species of mammals prefer to occupy habitats near to humans, while other mammalian species prefer disturbed habitats (Bateman and Fleming, 2012; Azad *et al.*, 2018. Chughtai *et al.*, 2018; Manzoor *et al.*, 2018; Safeer *et al.*, 2018; Younus *et al.*, 2018; Rasheed *et al.*, 2020). There are various approaches applied historically to measure biological diversity. This approach ranges from specie richness basic counting to complex measurement of evolutionary diversity (Calba *et al.*, 2014; Monnet *et al.*, 2014; González-Maya *et al.*, 2016). Every aspect of the ecosystem is accessed by using complex measurement method and it provide information about functioning ecosystem (Spasojevic *et al.*, 2014), and also provide better planning for conservation (Diaz *et al.*, 2013).

As density of mammalian species in the North America was studied, that showed variability in the climate. This variability causes variations in the structure of ecosystem and species density of North American mammals (Badgley and Fox, 2000). Ecological structure and density of mammalian species in Europe reflect it's physiographic and climate (Heikinheimo *et al.*, 2007). Most Australian mammalian

species occupy the Seaside Mountains and dissected levels of eastern and northeastern Australia contrasted with the large marsh desert interior. Although Asian mammals are not equally distributed, which show the eastern Himalayas and mountains have great species richness as compared to the low lands. There is also high risk of extinction in Himalayas of southeastern Asia (Sechrest *et al.*, 2002, Schipper *et al.*, 2008). India is also blessed with great faunal biodiversity (Vijayakumar *et al.*, 2015).

HABITAT PREFERENCE OF RED FOX

Mammalian diversity changes from woods to densely populated slope. Many climate region on this earth experiences such changes, example of such change is red fox (*vulpes vulpes*) which is more residing in more populated areas, also found in pre-urban area. Red fox preferred warm places in Japan. Urbanization has its effect which created nation such as Europe, Australia, Asia and America (Uraguchi *et al.*, 2009). In England red fox lived in densely populated or in semi-populated areas present in freezing zone (Harris and Smith, 1987).

MAMMALIAN DIVERSITY

Pakistan is enriched with bio-geographic areas which are three in number out of six, In Pakistan Ethiopian, Oriental and Palearctic are bio-geographic areas. Therefore Pakistan is a blend of faunal and botanical diversity. 195 types of mammalian fauna are represented in Pakistan (Roberts, 2005a, b).

MAMMALIAN DISTRIBUTION ON THE EARTH

Ireland has a long history of well evolved mammals recording, with a period prior to publication of An Forsa Forbatha Atlases (Lamhna, 1979). Of specific note are a few huge scale study of the badger (Feore, 1994), the otter (Chapman and Chapman, 1982), the bunny (Reid *et al.*, 2007).

MAMMALIAN DISTRIBUTION IN BOLIVIA

Study revealed 36,900 specimens of mammals which reflect that Bolivia has three hundred and twenty seven mammalian species. There are more than twenty species of mammals which are remained to be discovered because these twenty species are new to science and also new to Bolivia. Many of subspecies name shows taxonomic history and it provide detailed information about geographic variation. Scientific names are assigned to each species and sub species in Bolivia. The taxonomic status of mammals in the Bolivia is observed. Mammalian variety was enlisted and their local habitats showed the each species distribution in Bolivia. In addition to native species of Bolivia domestic mammals were also observed. The number of mammalian species is fifty to one hundred and eighty in local areas. Study showed that Bolivia has four major faunal area, including lowland temperate zone, forested areas, lowland tropics and highland areas. The upland and lowland mammalian diversity is not related (Anderson, 1997).

MAMMALIAN DISTRIBUTION IN CHIHUAHUA

State of Chihuahua, Mexico has 6500 mammalian specimens which revealed 122 species; and state also has at least 17 other species. Number of mammalian species is thirty five to fifty five in any one area. Taxonomic status of each mammalian species is considered within Chihuahua. Mammalian species are mentioned and study revealed that Chihuahua has three major faunal areas such as grass to desert plateau, coastal plains and woody areas. This faunal diversity of area has correlation with vegetation, climate and geography (Anderson, 1972).

EFFECT OF INCREASING WORLD POPULATION

World human populations are now exceeding 7 billion. The exceeding populace took more than fifty thousand years to achieve first out of seven billion. However the rate of populace growing topped during 1960s, that amassing number for individuals has implied that every extra billion is increasing much fast in comparison with any time observed in past. In the event that populace growth rate remains same as it is now, International society extends total populace may be nine point three billion during year of 2050 (Bloom, 2011). Continuous increase in populace of humans is cause of threat to the diversity because continuous increase in human population has great demand of urbanization, intensification and industrialization. All these aspects results in additional population (Altaf *et al.*, 2013). Tanzania is a country which has been gifted with immense fauna and flora diversity. Great diversity is because of changes in climatic and geographical conditions present in the country. There is high diversity in the fauna and flora of Mauritius which is result of isolation, variation in topography, island location (Mbwambo *et al.*, 2007).

HUMAN EXERCISES CAUSE TERMINATION OF LOCAL SPECIES

Biodiversity is facing changes in the natural environment and human activities effect, for example human and road settlement (Tilman *et al.*, 1997; Chapin *et al.*, 2000; Bellemare *et al.*, 2002). There is tough form of interaction shown by mammalian diversity and surrounding. Changes in the environment cause disturbance because some species of mammals are not adapted to such environmental changes. Those mammalian species that are not adapted to environmental changes lead to death (Cooper-Ellis *et al.*, 1999; Lugo, 2008). It is bad luck of biodiversity that human activities impact is severe and permanent, without any chance of recovery (Connell, 1978). Major key factor of environment alteration and biodiversity threat is due to conversion of land at fast rate (Dale *et al.*, 2001). At present, there is loss of mammalian variety by remarkable speed (Levin, 2005; Steffen *et al.*, 2011). Many of mammals have direct exposure for these environmental fluctuations. It is not possible to predict the effect on the biodiversity. Due to harmful effect on biodiversity extinction results in removal of mammalian species completely (Redford, 1992). As abundance of mammals is decreased to reflect its death rate, there are some traits of biodiversity which are considered more worth for because dropping of biodiversity analyzed at specie level provide high extinction rate of mammals (Barnosky *et al.*, 2011). Biotic interaction of ecosystem is important because many traits are directly depending on biotic interaction (Nectivores show pollination and carnivores shoe interaction of predator and prey. But unfortunately major biodiversity component are

neglected. Instead of neglecting, importance should be provide to these critical markers) or give analysis of surrounding issues. Stability of ecosystem is disturbed and effect of disturbance increases continuously. This disturbance provides information's about highly suffered region in order to prevent such type of degradation. Moreover, loss of mammalian species in not only due to habitat loss, there are many other drivers which effects on species and populations (Ceballos *et al.*, 2002; Davidson *et al.*, 2009). Some ecologically important mammalian species have more chance of extinction in less time. Such species show loss of ecosystem (Cadotte *et al.*, 2011). Human disturbance and species of mammals at risk give information's about all drivers for ecological loss also provide idea about region of high degradation risk (Díaz *et al.*, 2013).

EFFECTS ON MAMMALIAN DIVERSITY

From past ten thousand years, ordinary flora has changed over for farming fields or numerous general mammalian species migrate to newly discover natural surroundings (Umair, 2018; Rasheed *et al.*, 2020; Ijaz and Adil, 2021). Species who are limited to specific natural environment leads to extinction (Bouma *et al.*, 1998). In present time, serious cultivation results in change in ladscape (Newton, 2004; Purtauf *et al.*, 2005; Stoate *et al.*, 2009; Altaf *et al.*, 2018) that created -ve effect upon presence or scattering numerous interaction of wildlife. Local peoples and non-domesticated animals have long term past that exhibit the visualized glimpse for such relation from religion, art of people, folklores and (Şekercioğlu *et al.*, 2012).

EFFECT ON MAMMALS DUE TO CHANGE IN TEMPERATURE

The change in worldwide temperature influences the diversity of mammals as temperature increments upset hibernation, diminish water accessibility within dry situations leads to high level change in climate conditions which become reason of sickness (Garcia-Solache and Casadevall, 2010).

EFFECT ON MAMMALS DUE TO REDUCTION IN PRECIPITATION:

In Africa there is decline of several species of large mammals and this decline is due to precipitation reduction. As precipitation decreases it results in the reduction of plants growth and risk of predation (Ogutu and Owen-Smith, 2003; Musiega and Kazadi, 2004).

EFFECT ON MAMMALS DUE TO HUMAN ACTIVITIES

Human populaces are in charge of the present loss of biodiversity over the world with environmental change, contamination, fragmentation, and natural surroundings degradation being the real drivers of extinction of mammal (Vitousek *et al.*, 1997; Afsheen *et al.*, 2020.). Street roads and other direct infrastructure are a noteworthy reason for loss of natural surroundings, discontinuity, and degradation around the world. All over the world, there are now an expected seven hundred and fifty million vehicles going on roughly 50 million km in public street roads (T. Langton, individual correspondence) and the street road system and traffic movement volumes are still expanding, especially in Eastern Europe, China, India, and Latin America. Investigation of human effects on biodiversity has been performed at the species

diversity level (e.g., as per the middle of the road unsettling influence speculation on decent variety, which expresses that nearby species diversity is boosted at a moderate level of aggravation) (Grime, 1973; Connell, 1978; Huston, 1979). However, this access does not consider workable changes that modify biological communities' or give chances to interface the useful qualities of natural diversity and ecological change (Hausner *et al.*, 2003). Recently, species useful attributes have gained high similarities (i.e., parts of a life form's phenotype that impact biological system level procedures) (Hillebrand and Matthiessen, 2009) because they provide a link between diversity of species and functioning of ecosystem (Díaz and Cabido, 2001; Lavorel and Garnier, 2002; Naeem *et al.*, 2009; Luck *et al.*, 2012). In this manner, information in related to the link between attributes of species and environmental traits is more important than specie richness to know about response of different groups of species (i.e., arrays) to human impacts because there are many functions observed in the ecosystem which can be associated with particular attributes (Sekercioğlu *et al.*, 2004). For instance, considerable roles that are played via carnivores in biological systems rely upon attributes that are related with their trophic habits of group (Duffy, 2002; Casula *et al.*, 2006; Farias and Jaksic, 2011).

ANTHROPOGENIC VARIABLES CAUSE COMPLEXITIES OF AREAS

The Neotropics is a region of this world which has more complexity and this region possesses more diversity (Schipper, 2008; Brown *et al.*, 2014). But Neotropics is more threatened area because of anthropogenic factors (González-Maya *et al.*, 2016; Le Saout *et al.*, 2013). As human interaction with Neotropic area increases, more efficient and effect full measures for conservation are required for betterment of area and reduce the level of biodiversity loss. All these measures help in the preservation of natural ecosystem of Neotropics (Ceballos *et al.*, 2005; Boitani *et al.*, 2011). It is necessary to know about the ecosystem drivers because this type of understanding helps in better planning for conservation of diversity (Armsworth *et al.*, 2007; Biswas *et al.*, 2011). Neotropics have almost no basic information's for taxonomic division of the area (Hoffmann *et al.*, 2014; Rondinini *et al.*, 2011). Recently all groups are studied to get information's about distribution pattern; status of conservation, variations, original state and large scale extinction, but it is difficult task to get all information's related to all aspects (Lees *et al.*, 2012). Some previous examination approached the magnitude of land changes takes place in Neotropic area (Sánchez-Cuervo *et al.*, 2012), but according to our information less study have relatedness to change in functioning of ecosystem and diversity functioning (Barragán *et al.*, 2010; Biswas *et al.*, 2010). Moreover, at global scale mammalian diversity has been studied (Ceballos *et al.*, 2005), but less assessment of mammalian diversity has done at regional level (González-Maya *et al.*, 2016; Farias *et al.*, 2014; Ceballos *et al.*, 2007). Currently many African countries, especially in South Africa, focused on the rural development and people of African countries also set some principles for rural development. Local population is responsible for their traditional land planning's. Educated people understand the importance of mammals and they support the conservational planning (Happold, 1995).

ANTHROPOGENIC EFFECT ON MAMMALIAN DIVERSITY

Anthropogenic effects highly influenced the species of mammals. Some mammalian species have adaptations to adjust in the environment but other become extinct and rare. Anthropogenic effects in ecosystem cause extinction of mammalian species. Due to anthropogenic effects mammalian diversity is lost at dangerous level (Pimm *et al.*, 1995; Regan *et al.*, 2001; Fatima *et al.*, 2019; Jahangeer *et al.*, 2019; Kanwal *et al.*, 2019). As human population increases rapidly, it has negative effect on the diversity present in the world. The harmful effect of this increase in population includes change in climate, cutting of forests, pollution (Saba *et al.*, 2020) and habitat loss of species (Bierwagen, 2007). There is difference of environment between urban areas and natural habitats. New residential areas are developed with better facilities which separated the large ecosystem into natural and urbanized land (McKinney, 1946), it cause removal of natural vegetative areas or there are many decorative mammals makeshift natural mammalian diversity has replaced with ornamental species (Holway and Suarez, 2006). Due to anthropogenic effect of human beings the natural ecosystem modified and changed into forest area, urban and peri urban area. Urbanizations also enhance the diversity of mammals as it facilitate with different places for making refuge (Blair, 1996).

MAMMALIAN LIFE LOSS IN NATIONAL PARKS

In National Park known as Denali, there were moose which do not visit places with more traffic on the roads, but “caribou and grizzly bear are not observed to avoid road traffic” (Yost and Wright, 2001). There is negative effect of the wildlife-human interaction on the mammals of national park which results in death of wildlife on rail line and roads. As vehicles collision incidence take place in the national park results in loss of thousands dollars due to damage. Human injuries and deaths are also observed each year (Conover *et al.*, 1995).

MAMMALS FACING PROBLEMS IN CANADA NATIONAL PARKS

Most research has done to avoid the accidents in the rocky mountains of national parks. According to wildlife point of view ecological perspective is threatened because of many of mammalian species loss from native populace because of traffic on highway and many impacts of human population. Especially mammalian species need more concern and with less reproductive potential are died in road accidents (Romin and Bissonnette, 1996).

WILD BEAR AND WOLF MORTALITY IN JASPER AND SAGUARO NATIONAL PARK

In Jasper National Park managers are present and their responsibility is to maintain the mortality of the wildlife by humans less than 1 percent for gizzly bear and wolves species. This step is also taken for the mammals which have more chances of mortality by the human’s activities. Visitor create disturbance in the saguaro national park in Arizona which cause the mortality of mammalian species, especially desert bighorn sheep (Harris *et al.*, 1995).

TEMPERATURE CHANGE DUE TO ANTHROPOGENIC EXERCISES

Anthropogenic exercises such as, urbanization, farming practices or industrial development is major driver for a worldwide temperature alteration or environmental change (Saino *et al.*, 2011). Study about harmful impact of smoke has been started during 17th century and it cause acid rain phenomenon during 1950s. Ecological niche of species have interaction of multiple environmental factors. For example, specie population does not show growth under warm and arid or wet and cool environment, but show high growth at high temperature under moist conditions. If mammalian species have ability to tolerate the effect of human activities then same interaction between species niche and intensity of human activities might be observed. For example, species of mammals may have ability to tolerate hunting in moist habitat, but in dry environment negative growth rate intensity observed. Natural selection favours the mammalian species who adapted the change in the local environment (Antonovics *et al.*, 1976).

MIGRATION OF MAMMALS DUE TO CHANGE IN TEMPERATURE

Animals are distributed to different areas are affected by the change in the climate (Ruegg *et al.*, 2006). Migratory mammals have especially effect of climate change. There are many species of migratory mammals, 26 to 27% migratory mammals moved back for places to breed 2 weeks before (Sparks and Menzel, 2002) in last 3 decided migratory species migrate due to increase in temperature. But when there is condition of decrease in temperature then mammals do not return to their places earlier. Change in time id inversely proportional to the distance, because in case of greater distance arrival time of mammals will decreased (Saino *et al.*, 2011).

FOSSIL EVIDENCES OF MAMMALS

Mammalian data of fossil remains allows the comparison of coexisting collection from low and uplands. It is noted that richness of species in greater in upland assemblage. Early Cenozoic example revealed that well sampled, Middle Eocene mammalian diversity were compared from the different areas of Green River Basin in Wyoming, USA including basin-center and basin-margin (Gunnell and Bartels, 2001). The basin- center is site of highly rising mountains blessed with greater specie richness of mammals and also contain some other groups of vertebrates. Probably, higher richness showed that ecotone is between lowland and upland habitats. Many groups of mammals demonstrated proof of speciation in situ (progenitor relative sets or sister species with a hereditary species in a more established interim). A late Cenozoic example revealed the fossil assemblages contrast from Miocene of china and Pakistan countries. In floodplain dregs(sediments) from the Himalayan for eland basin of Pakistan, the best specie richness of mammalian assemblage over twelve-million years time span was seventy species recorded at 10 million years back (Barry *et al.*, 2002). In contrast late Miocene fossil territory at a similar latitude from a montane valley in Southwestern China conserved one hundred and twenty species (Badgley *et al.*, 1988).

Changes in height and relief cause change in climatic and air conditions, habitat, and connection among different habitats. For land mammals, the operational properties are continuity (Coblentz and Riitters, 2004). There are some regions which

are active and passive and such areas occupy comparable areas likewise, some trophic groups reflect high montane specie richness, such as herbivores, where as omnivores and carnivores do not show high specie (Badgley and Fox, 2000).

FACTORS INVOLVED IN MAMMALIAN MORTALITY

Some Human-mammals interactions are considered as detrimental factors to wild mammalian species. In Africa geographical distribution and number of mammalian population have been reduced because of modification of habitat, hunting of many species and to avoid disease spread by some species. Specie location, habitat preferences and human population density is important to know the effect of human-mammals interaction. Some different sized species also get advantage from human population, so there is increase in the number of such species in highly conserved and protected areas. Human and mammalian density has strong negative relation (Happold, 1995). The main purpose of road ecological study is to get information about ecological effects of road on diversity. Study of road ecology has aim to reduce or avoid negative effects on ecosystem. This study showed many adverse effects of road traffic on mammalian diversity. Harmful effect involves loss of habitat, high mortality rate of wildlife. This loss of mammalian diversity is due to collision of mammals with vehicles, effect of moisture and wind and pollution due to traffic. For example, noise, light and chemical substances facilitate dispersal of mammals. Street road also have harmful effect on the human range but research on this point is still uncompleted (Di Giulio and Holderegger, 2009). Understanding the effects of streets road and heavy traffic one must know about reason of diversity loss. Natural habitats of mammals have been damaged and used the lands for agricultural purposes from ten thousand years (Bouma and Droogers, 1998). Therefore, agricultural use of natural habitats have been begin when there was end of twentieth hundred years at the end of 20th century (Pimentel *et al.*, 2004) and this practice have appeared in dispute among mammalian diversity and human population. However, it is need for humans to increase agricultural places to fulfill food requirements, but there also need to conserve mammals. Humans damaged nearly every ecosystem but their role of conserving mammalian species can never be denied (Henle *et al.*, 2008).

NEED TO PRESERVE THE BIODIVERSITY LOSS

Conservation of the mammalian species important phenomenon but it is bad luck that resources present in ecosystem are not enough for conservation planning's. Available resources are unable to stop the loss of the earth's threatened mammalian. There is requirement of field of science which deals with the conservation planning's. Due to increase in human population and their increasing effect on the mammalian diversity due to ignorance, there is rapid loss of biodiversity (Mace, 1995). There is need to know important diversity impacts for better assessment of diversity removal and to try to maintain the level of biodiversity. Furthermore, to solve the problems of threatening the mammals it is vital to assess the effects on biodiversity pattern. The biologists dealing with the conservation have knowledge of current level of extinction because this awareness enables the biologists to plan conservation in better way (Purvis *et al.*, 2005b).

PREVENTIONS TO SAVE MAMMALS ON ROAD

The important step is to know that how the density of road system have its effect on the functional relation among ecosystems at scale of landscape. Answer to this question will provide information about the planning for transportations and environmental assessment (Roedenbeck *et al.*, 2007).

Harassment involves the events which cause activities disturbance, happiness, stress and also death of mammals. Some time humans do harassment by their intention, sometimes visitors try to gain the attention of mammals and chase them or throw objects at mammalian species (Wright, 1992). But sometimes humans harass the mammalian diversity unintentionally. Such as use of different motors on road cause displacement of mammals, increase the range of their home and also effect on the mammalian activity pattern (Cottureau, 1972; Freddy *et al.*, 1986; King and Workman, 1986; Kuss *et al.*, 1990). Human exercises, including more trail use by individuals, affected natural surroundings of grizzly bears (Hood and Parker, 2001). More traffic on the street roads alters the feeding and movement pattern of wild mammals (Mattson *et al.*, 1987).

CONSERVATION OF MAMMALS IN AFRICA

Currently, many African countries involved in the formations of principle for development of rural areas. In this planning local people of rural areas are involved in administration of their traditional lands. In Africa it is observed that people residing near the mammalian conservation areas know the importance of conservation planning. People who are highly educated know importance of conservation very well. Conservation in the countries of Africa only advantage full if there is great participation by the peoples. Conservation is possible by decreasing the rate of human population, by stabilizing human population densities and set programmes to educate people about conservation of mammalian species (Happold *et al.*, 1995).

IMPORTANCE OF MAMMALS

Mammals are important for ecosystem and play a role as bioindicators (Altaf, 2018; Sidra *et al.*, 2019; Babar and Kanwal, 2021). Large sized mammalian carnivores (species in the order Carnivora) are ecologically vital because individual have direct or indirect effect on the ecosystem and community of the earth (Ripple and Beschta, 2004). There are some local habitat factors, including complexity in the habitat structure may be have considerable effect on the predation (Bertolino, 2007) and local populace elements (Spencer *et al.*, 2005), while landscape configuration also influence on specie richness, structure of populace and dispersal success (Henein *et al.*, 1998; Westerberg *et al.*, 2005).

MAMMALS HELP IN POLLINATION

Numerous undomesticated mammalian species considered helpful in pollination and also helpful in scattering of plans seeds. Some mammalian species observed which provide help in supporting biological system or reusing of nutritional material (Heine and Speir, 1989). World health organization concluded that the majority of the total populace is fundamentally dependent on medications derived from animals. Out of

252 essential chemicals that have been chosen by the World Health Organization, 8.7% got from animals (Marques *et al.*, 1997).

MAMMALS AS ENVIRONMENTAL INDICATOR

The land animals such as mammals are considered as environmental indicator and helpful in indentifying conservation areas. By knowing the inhabiting area of specie, their distribution record in history and estimating threat level to specie help in doing effort for specie protection (Myers, 1990; Myers *et al.*, 2000).

ROLE OF IUCN IN CONSERVATION OF THREATENED SPECIES

At the worldwide scale the best way of collecting data on the preservation status of animals is the IUCN Red List of Threatened Species. The Red List gives taxonomic, protection status and distribution data on taxa that have been assessed by using IUCN Red List Categories and Criteria. This system is made to decide the relative chance of extinction, with the main purpose of highlighting the taxa that are at the great risk of extinction (i.e., those recorded as Critically Endangered, Endangered and Vulnerable). The IUCN Red List is proposed to approach the policy which is used to educate preservation and priority planning's process, but it is not biodiversity conserving priority system (IUCN, 2001).

The IUCN Red List classifications and criteria are proposed to be an effortlessly and broadly comprehended framework for characterizing species at high danger of worldwide eradication. The general point of the framework is to give an unequivocal, target system for the arrangement of the broadest scope of species as indicated by their eradication chance (IUCN, 2001). Different variants of the IUCN framework have been being used for more than 40 years, yet since the late 1990s the classes and criteria have experienced a broad audit to deliver a clearer, generally appropriate, open and simple to-utilize framework. Lately the IUCN have additionally given nitty gritty direction on the most proficient method to apply the classes and criteria (IUCN, 2008). Appropriation of the IUCN framework guarantees consistency and equivalence crosswise over scientific classifications and areas. The IUCN have given direction on the most proficient method to apply the red rundown classifications and criteria on a provincial level (IUCN, 2003).

EXTINCTION OF MAMMALS DUE TO LOSS OF GEOGRAPHICAL RANGES

The geographic ranges of numerous species are made up of multiple associating local populations (Andrewartha *et al.*, 1986). There is focus on the extirpation of local population of area, range loss and extinction process helps in the conservation efforts. For instance, study about range loss attain attention of declining species before their extinction (Caughley, 1994) and this process of focusing helps in revealing the range loss drivers and provide sense of management (Schonewald-Cox *et al.*, 1983). If there is a specie which is still common in world then studying range loss can identify ecosystem where local population of given specie is losing (Ceballos *et al.*, 2002). Although it is understood that human brings various modifications in environment which are main extinction driver of biodiversity (Channell *et al.*, 2000), there is continuous discussion about the role of many other factors, including intraspecific variety in defenselessness play in deciding pattern of range loss. Various authors have

estimated that the spatial dispersion of appropriate environmental conditions (counting biotic cooperations) (Holt *et al.*, 2009) leads to change in the demography and size of local population and this type of change effect the ability of population to tolerate disturbance due to anthropogenic (Lawton, 1993).

The range structure and elements that outcome from the interaction among the individual of the species and distribution pattern of related environmental conditions within range of species are not understandable without simplification (Holt *et al.*, 2005). Specie ecological niche is the way that ecologist used to made sense of complexity. A set of conditions followed by species have high growth rate or zero is known as specie ecological niche (Hutchinson *et al.*, 1992). The Human-mammals interaction also influence the growth rate of many mammalian species. (Counting collaborations with ecological changes related with people such land utilize change orhunting), and we focus on the point that response of species against the human interaction should be part of specie niche. It is important to know that some species of mammals have high growth rate by the human action which facilitate the range expansion (Kanda *et al.*, 2009).

CULTURAL IMPORTANCE OF MAMMALS

Some people in rural areas used present resources which have not importance evenly. The thought about importance of cultural values arose with the traditionally used system of classification and assigning taxa (Berlin, 2014). There are different categories which follows different selection parameters of specific or group of species (Rosegrant, 2000; Milton, 2003; Kamanga *et al.*, 2009). Mammalian species ecological attributes, advantages acquired from them, their direct and indirect harm to environment, their cultural values and other aspects are considered while allocate values to them (del Valle *et al.*, 2015). Cultural value of mammals is a scientific method and it involves different social and ecological process which proceeded in different way in different era (Ruan-Soto *et al.*, 2013).

HUNTING OF MAMMALS BY HUMANS

The extraordinary needs experienced by these networks are frequently prompt chasing of wild fauna for purposes of getting food (Hanazaki *et al.*, 2009).

MAMMALIAN USE FOR HUMANS IN ENVIRONMENT

The wildlife and biodiversity has useful values for humans, which include direct and indirect values. Values having straight utilization are arrangement for nourishment, medicine, habitat, wearing stuff and so forth. But values have not directly utilization are large cluster for significance biological system administrations for arrangement of pure ventilation to H₂O (Mols and Visser, 2007).

USE OF MAMMALS FOR MAKING DIFFERENT PURPOSES

Humans used animals for making different materials from ancient time. Human utilize mammals for making food (Pinto *et al.*, 2010), articles of clothing, different tools, Formation of meds and enchanted religious practices dates to the early history of humankind (Frazier *et al.*, 2007). Such uses have caused impacts that frequently exploited the abused species (Alves *et al.*, 2012). A few examinations demonstrate

socio economic disadvantage of use of mammalian species present in surrounding (Koster *et al.*, 2008; Pattiselanno *et al.*, 2004). Such a circumstance exists in a vast population occupy the semi-arid areas of northeastern Brazil (Alves *et al.*, 2009; Barbosa, 2011).

USE OF MAMMALS FOR MAGIC

Many byproducts of mammals are utilized for magical religious purposes (Bezerra *et al.*, 2013).

ARCTIC ANIMALS USE IN MAKING ORNAMENTAL ITEMS

Numerous Arctic people groups have depend on the mammalian variety of the ocean, and they proceed with this type of vocation now a days. Whiskery seals, beluga, bowhead, and narwhal whales, walrus, and polar bears are mammals utilized by Arctic people for garments, nourishment products or auxiliary items. These mammals number overwhelmingly in the blended money or subsistence economy of local families and networks (Huntington, 1992; Hovelsrud-Broda, 1999; Caulfield, 2000).

ROLE OF MAMMALS IN FORESTRY ACTIVITIES

Wild mammals have been important throughout history for many value full reasons beside nutritional and consumptive uses. Wildlife has central value to the religious customs and folklore. These representative values of wild mammals are still valuable today in almost all communities of this earth. Currently, no use of forest wild animals has considered in calculation of “forest values” and there is not any list of benefits obtained from forests. There is not any knowledge to population about forestry scheme (Peters *et al.*, 1989). Although it is reported by many of ecologists that large mammals have their important role in the pollination, dispersal of plants seed, predation process, and herbivory. All these processes are not possible if these wild mammals would remove from the earth. More work on shows those large mammals in the tropical forests plays important ecological roles. If large mammals remove from ecosystem then it will change the forest. If ecological sustainability require for long term then increase the mammalian diversity to maintain forestry activity (Redford, 1992).

ZOOTHERAPY

At the time of Egypt and many other ancient Baylonian, Assyrian and Mesopotamia practice of zotherapy was made (Lev, 2003). In history practice of zotherapy have not given much importance and neglected because of more favorable work of ethnobotany. More survey work has done on medicines made by plants. However, currently zotherapy become more interest able for the researchers and people from different fields aroused and started their research on the ethnozoology. Researchers from different fields found use of animals in remedial process (Costa- Lohani, 2010).

In this world hunters preferred mammalian species for hunting to use them as their food. Ladies have more information to make herbal medicines (Lucena *et al.*, 2011) and zotherapeutic items (Ferreira *et al.*, 2009). Studies show that getting knowledge about the natural resources started at individuals young age (Schwartz *et al.*,

2006; Silva, 2011). Age and knowledge of individuals have direct relation with each other (Monteiro, 2006).

Mammals are used to derive 8.7% of highly essential chemical from their body (Marques *et al.*, 1997). In many communities of humans mammals used as major source of protein. Mammals are also used in leather industries (Del Valle *et al.*, 2015). From ancient time human being are well aware of animals use in field food, medicine, cloth and so on (Alves *et al.*, 2012). Traditional medicines are mostly used in low income Traditional medication is the most effortlessly available and moderate type of treatment in poor countries because this therapy is easily accessible without much cost (Alves *et al.*, 2011). Zootherapy is a phenomenon which is distributed geographically and also has its historic records (Marques *et al.*, 1994). Zootherapy involve healing trials (Bagde and Hampa, 2013). Zootherapy is considered a valueable alternative in modern society (Alves *et al.*, 2005). Therefore, in order to know the important relationship, it is important to consider the ethnozoology as effective field to treat diseases. Traditional bonding between local people and mammalian species should be considered (Londoño-Betancourth *et al.*, 2009). Animals are used to make medicines is one of important part of traditional based knowledge throughout the world most old cultures have made practice of animal based therapy treatment (Weiss, 1947; Lev, 2003) and such practice is still continue with many new societies. Animal based products have healing effective for humans (MacKinney, 1946). Animal derived product such as teeth, skin, nails, horns milk, faeces, urine, oil, and eggs have their importance in treating many diseases (Alves and Rosa 2005; Magige *et al.*, 2009). Method of using variety of medicines to treat same disease is more popular because it permits animal availability. Different species of mammals can be used for same medicinal properties because some medicinal mammals used for same purpose and it indicates effectiveness of zootherapeutic treatment (Alves and Rosa, 2006).

China has more use of traditional medicines. It is noted that almost 1500 species of animals used in Chinese traditional medicines. These Chinese traditional medicines are used to treat all kind of diseases (Mahawar and Jaroli, 2008). In india there are 109 animals used in the traditional medicines. 250 animals of Northeast Brazil have been used in the traditional medicines (Alves and Rosa, 2005). In Africa, there are many animals which are surely used to treat many diseases in South Africa, Ghana and Nigeria (Adeola, 1992). Moreover, animal's raw products have been used for trading in the abroad. In Asian countries these exported products of animals are used in formation of traditional medicines. Animal products are used in many societies for cultural use and this practice increase the development of the animal based medicines all over the world. Excessive use of animals for medicinal used cause the extinction of many species (Cavaliere, 2010). In Brazil, more than 180 therapeutic animals have been recorded (Alves *et al.*, 2011; Alves and Rosa, 2005). In India, incredible work was done in the field of zootherapy; traditionally made medicines are reported in the work of Charaka samhita and Ayurveda. In India mammals use in medicine is common practice. Last decade of India has importance, because at that time interest has been taken in study of ethnozoology (Vijayakumar *et al.*, 2015).

Various animals are reported in Ayurvedic work done in field of zootherapy, which involves forty one Mammals (Tripathy *et al.*, 1995). Different present peoples and their ancestors made use of animals to treat different diseases in India. The Hindu religion has utilized five items (drain, pee, excrement, curd and ghee) of the cow for purifying process since from old time (Simoons *et al.*, 1974).

Recently it is reported that in Mauritius there is use of animal based therapy. Study was done to get awareness about the use of animals for giving treatment in mauritias. People of the area have used animals to make medicines which are helpful in treatment of different diseases (Mootoosamy *et al.*, 2014).

In Nigeria Wild mammals and their products are used by the farmers. According to research the agriculturists used wild mammals for their religious occasions, cultural use and medicinal use. Wild mammalian species are very important for rural population. Habitats of the wild mammals are used to fulfill projects planned by the agriculturists. So modification takes place on the mammalian habitats and there is great destruction of habitats. Farmers used this land for their cultivation. The wild mammals included in important renewable resources which provide advantages continuously if there is sufficient availability of habitat and protection (Adeola, 1992).

Tanzania is a country that is provided with the great animal biodiversity, because of high variation in the climatic conditions present in the country. In Tanzania presence of traditional medicines is from old time. Medicine plays an important role in colonial era. Colonialists in Tanzania wanted to rule in Africa, so colonialists wanted to degrade all type of activities which could be cause of providing chance to Africans for development of their country (Mbwambo *et al.*, 2007).

Wild animals had made a huge contribution in the betterment of humans because mammals provide direct source of food. Wild mammals are helpful for survival of the people live in rural area and depend on the forest. In different developing countries, people living in the rural area are provided with the major part of protein by the wild mammals. It is observed by the study of 60 countries that human average diet has protein components and 20 percent of protein is added by the wild mammals and protein percentage is greater in the diet of people living in poor and rural parts of the country. It is estimated that 75% of People of sub-Saharan Africa largely rely on the protein source obtained from traditional (Aisbey, 1974).

HUMAN-MAMMALS CONFLICT

Wild life human interaction normally has been classified in three different ways: 1) Non domestic mammals conflict with individuals, 2) individuals getting a amusement of wildlife, and 3) individuals have negative influence on wildlife. With each of this class various groups of people have different association, which cause people-people conflict about different nature's existing problems and application of different management actions (Riley *et al.*, 2002). Conflict could be as small as a burden for people, as bigger as anthropoid damage or mortality, and it is perception that population of humans have increased chances of injury or mortality. Mostly obvious clashes are present among people and mammals. For example, bears, different flesh eating mammals, and hoofed animals (Kuss *et al.*, 1990).

MAMMALS CAUSE DANGER FOR HUMANS

Jasper national park also shows the human-wildlife clash (Weaver *et al.*, 1996). Lions in mountain areas, wolves or buffalo cause harms to the visitors by attacking on them (Riley and Decker, 2000; Braithwaite and McCool, 1989). Intermediate attackers, for example, wildcats likewise source of clashes with individuals, particularly in area of parks which is developed or in parks close to urban zones (Bounds and Shaw, 1994; Harris *et al.*, 1997). The bases of these clashes are either cause of fear or chance of danger to the human and pet safety (e.g., from coyotes). Other recorded clashes among wild mammals and people involve predation (e.g., coyotes and wolves) attack on pets of visitors, worry for shifting of disease to people visit parks e.g., rabies in bats and for domestic animals living close to the park e.g., brucellosis in buffalo (Inserro, 1997). The meadow in urbanscape region is influenced by the grass eating mammals living in forests (Studsrod and Wegge, 1995). Thus, animals in urbanscape territories are harmfully influenced by the non domestic flesh eating mammals and connoisseur residing in close to this region. Well evolved creatures for the most part harm the harvests around evening time (Sekhar, 1998). Mammals harm fourteen percent of cereal and twenty four percent of corn per area unit annually. Additionally, two percent death rate of the local domesticated animals calculated because of the attack by panther, wolf, lynx and bear. This loss cause clash between human and non domesticated mammals and humans kill many mammalian attacker mammals in return. The mammalian variety is under ceaseless danger from sick impacts of urbanization that caused division of biological systems, farming places, pollution and alter pattern of climate (Din *et al.*, 2013).

MAMMALS AND ZONOTIC DISEASES

Mammals play a main role in human being life. Human interactions with mammals can create a threat and can be transferred diseases to human being. People who have close contact with animals in home, zoo and nature can be at threat for zoonotic diseases (Altaf, 2020).

REFERENCES

- Abbasi, Z. 2021. Diversity and folklore medicinal uses of mammalian species of Harighal, Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Pakistan. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 5: 60-65.
- Adeola, M. O. 1992. Importance of wild animals and their parts in the culture, religious festivals, and traditional medicine, of Nigeria. *Environmental conservation*. 19(2): 125-134.
- Afsheen, S., S. Adil, S. Ijaz, H. Aslam, R. Kanwal. 2020. A brief study of mammals-A review *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 4: 51-70.
- Afsheen, S., S. Adil, S. Ijaz, H. Aslam, R. Kanwal. 2020. A brief study of mammals-A review *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 4: 51-70.
- Altaf, M. 2016. Assessment of Avian and Mammalian Diversity at Selected Sites along river Chenab. University of Veterinary and Animal Sciences, Lahore, Pakistan.
- Altaf, M. 2017. First record of Small Indian Civet (*Viverricula indica*) from Azad Jammu and Kashmir Himalaya-Pakistan. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 1: 17-24.
- Altaf, M. 2018. Study of human-mammals conflict and interaction-A review *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 2: 20-24.

- Altaf, M. 2018. Study of human-mammals conflict and interaction-A review *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 2: 20-24.
- Altaf, M. 2020. Wild animals as source of Zoonotic diseases-a review. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 4: 71-84.
- Altaf, M., A. Javid, M. Umair, K.J. Iqbal, Z. Rasheed, A.M. Abbasi. 2017. Ethnomedicinal and cultural practices of mammals and birds in the vicinity of river Chenab, Punjab-Pakistan. *Journal of ethnobiology and ethnomedicine*. 13: 41.
- Altaf, M., D.Javid, M.A.Irfan, S.A.Munir, K.J.Iqbal, M.Umair, and A.M.Khan. 2013. Diversity,distribution and ecology of birds in summer season flathead Khanki,Punjab,Pakistan.*Biologia(Pakistan)*. 59: 131-137.
- Altaf, M., M. Umair, A.R. Abbasi, N. Muhammad, A.M. Abbasi. 2018. Ethnomedicinal applications of animal species by the local communities of Punjab, Pakistan. *Journal of ethnobiology and ethnomedicine*. 14: 55.
- Altaf, M., S. Nazer, Musarat, I. Manzoor, B. Safeer, S. Yasrub. 2018. Study of human activities impacts and interaction with small Indian mongoose in Dhirkot, district Bagh, Azad Jammu and Kashmir. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 2: 31-37.
- Alves, R. R. N., W. M. S. Souto. 2015. Ethnozoology: a brief introduction. *Ethnobiology and Conservation*. 4.
- Alves, R. R., I. L. Rosa, 2006. From cnidarians to mammals: The use of animals as remedies in fishing communities in NE Brazil. *Journal of ethnopharmacology*. 107(2): 259-276.
- Alves, R. R., I. L. Rosa, G. G. Santana. 2007. The role of animal-derived remedies as complementary medicine in Brazil. *AIBS Bulletin*. 57(11): 949-955.
- Alves, R. R., I. L. Rosa, N. A. Neto, R. Voeks. 2012. Animals for the gods: magical and religious faunal use and trade in Brazil. *Journal of Human Ecology*. 40(5): 751-780.
- Alves, R. R., I. L. Rosa. 2005. Why study the use of animal products in traditional medicines?. *Journal of Ethnobiology and Ethnomedicine*. 1(1): 5.
- Alves, R. R., L. E. Mendonça, M. V. Confessor, W. L. Vieira, L. C. Lopez. 2009. Hunting strategies used in the semi-arid region of northeastern Brazil. *Journal of ethnobiology and ethnomedicine*. 5(1): 12.
- Alves, R., J. A. Barbosa, S. L. Santos, W. Souto, R. R. Barboza. 2011. Animal-based remedies as complementary medicines in the semi-arid region of northeastern Brazil. *Complementary and Alternative Medicine*. 8(1): 44.
- Anderson, S. (1997). Mammals of Bolivia: taxonomy and distribution. *Bulletin of the AMNH*: 231.
- Anderson, S. 1972. Mammals of Chihuahua: taxonomy and distribution. *Bulletin of the AMNH*. 148(2).
- Antonovics, J. 1976. The nature of limits to natural selection. *Annals of the Missouri Botanical Garden*: 224-247.
- Armsworth, P. R., K. M. A. Chan, G. C. Daily, P. R. Ehrlich, C. Kremen, T. H. Ricketts, M. A. Sanjayan. 2007. Ecosystem-service science and the way forward for conservation. *Conservation biology*.21(6): 1383-1384.
- Asibey, E. O. 1974. Wildlife as a source of protein in Africa south of the Sahara. *Biological conservation*. 6(1): 32-39.

- Aslam, H., M. Faiz. 2020. Ethnopharmacological and modern applications of milk of various mammalian species-a review. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 4: 211-226.
- Azad, M., M. Altaf, B. Safeer, I. Manzoor, S. Yasrub. 2018. Assessment of human-red fox conflict in district Bagh, Azad Jammu and Kashmir. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 2: 1-10.
- Babar, M., R. Kanwal. 2021. Wildlife as a bioindicator-a review *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 5: 139-145.
- Badgley, C. 1988. Paleogeology of a Miocene, tropical, upland fauna: Lufeng. China. *Nation. Geogr.* 4: 178-195.
- Badgley, C., D. L. Fox. 2000. Ecological biogeography of North American mammals: species density and ecological structure in relation to environmental gradients. *Journal of Biogeography*. 27(6): 1437-1467.
- Bagde, N., J. Hampa. 2013. An ethnozoological studies and medicinal values of vertebrate origin in the adjoining areas of Pench National Park of Chhindwara District of Madhya Pradesh, India. *Ind Int.J Life Sci*. 1: 278-83.
- Barnosky, A. D., N. Matzke, S. Tomiya, G. O. Wogan, B. Swartz, T. B. Quental, B. Mersey. 2011. Has the Earth's sixth mass extinction already arrived?. *Nature*. 471(7336): 51.
- Barragán, F., C. E. Moreno, F. Escobar, G. Halffter, D. Navarrete. 2011. Negative impacts of human land use on dung beetle functional diversity. *PloS one*. 6(3): e17976.
- Barry, J. C., M. E. Morgan, L. J. Flynn, D. Pilbeam, A. K. Behrensmeyer, S. M. Raza, J. Kelley. 2002. Faunal and environmental change in the late Miocene Siwaliks of northern Pakistan. *Paleobiology*. 28(S2): 1-71.
- Bateman, P. W., P. A. Fleming. 2012. Big city life: carnivores in urban environments. *Journal of Zoology*. 287(1): 1-23.
- Bellemare, J., G. Motzkin, D. R. Foster. 2002. Legacies of the agricultural past in the forested present: an assessment of historical land-use effects on rich mesic forests. *Journal of Biogeography*. 29(10-11): 1401-1420.
- Berlin, B. 2014. *Ethnobiological classification: Principles of categorization of plants and animals in traditional societies*. Princeton University Press. Vol. 185.
- Bertolino, S. 2007. Microhabitat use by garden dormice during nocturnal activity. *Journal of Zoology*. 272(2): 176-182.
- Bezerra, D. M. M., H. F. P. de Araujo, Â. G. C. Alves, R. R. N. Alves. 2013. Birds and people in semiarid northeastern Brazil: symbolic and medicinal relationships. *Journal of Ethnobiology and Ethnomedicine*. 9(1): 3.
- Bierwagen, B. G. 2007. Connectivity in urbanizing landscapes: The importance of habitat configuration, urban area size, and dispersal. *Urban Ecosystems*. 10(1): 29-42.
- Biswas, S. R., A. U. Mallik. 2011. Species diversity and functional diversity relationship varies with disturbance intensity. *Ecosphere* 2(4): 1-10.
- Blair, R. B. 1996. Land use and avian species diversity along an urban gradient. *Ecological applications*. 6(2): 506-519.
- Bloom, D. E. 2011. 7 billion and counting. *Science*, 333(6042): 562-569.

- Boitani, L., L. Maiorano, D. Baisero, A. Falcucci, P. Visconti, C. Rondinini. 2011. What spatial data do we need to develop global mammal conservation strategies?. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London B: Biological Sciences*. 366(1578): 2623-2632.
- Bouma, J., P. Droogers. 1998. A procedure to derive land quality indicators for sustainable agricultural production. *Journal of Geoderma*. 85(1): 103-110.
- Bounds, D. L., W. W. Shaw. 1994. Managing coyotes in US National Parks: Human-coyote interactions. *Natural Areas Journal*. 14(4): 280-284.
- Braithwaite, A. M., S. F. Mccool. 1989. Social influences and backcountry visitor behavior in occupied grizzly bear habitat. *Society & Natural Resources*. 2(1): 273-283.
- Brown, J. H. 2014. Why are there so many species in the tropics?. *Journal of biogeography*. 41(1): 8-22.
- Cadotte, M. W., K. Carscadden, N. Mirotchnick. 2011. Beyond species: functional diversity and the maintenance of ecological processes and services. *Journal of applied ecology*. 48(5): 1079-1087.
- Calba, S., V. Maris, V. Devictor. 2014. Measuring and explaining large-scale distribution of functional and phylogenetic diversity in birds: separating ecological drivers from methodological choices. *Global Ecology and Biogeography* 23(6): 669-678.
- Casula, P., A. Wilby, M. B. Thomas. 2006. Understanding biodiversity effects on prey in multi-enemy systems. *Ecology Letters*. 9(9):995-1004.
- Caughley G. 1994. Directions in conservation biology. *Journal of Animal, Ecol* . 63: 215–244.
- Caulfield, R. A. 2000. Political economy of renewable resources in the Arctic. *The Arctic: environment, people, policy*. 485-513.
- Cavaliere, C. 2010. Medicinal use of threatened animal species and the search for botanical alternatives. *Herbal Gram*,.86: 34-49.
- Ceballos, G. 2007. Conservation priorities for mammals in megadiverse Mexico: the efficiency of reserve networks. *Ecological Applications*. 17(2): 569-578.
- Ceballos, G., P. R. Ehrlich, J. Soberón, I. Salazar, J. P. Fay. 2005. Global mammal conservation: what must we manage?. *Science*. 309(5734): 603-607.
- Ceballos, G., P. R. Ehrlich. 2002. Mammal population losses and the extinction crisis. *Science*.296(5569): 904-907.
- Channell, R., M. V. Lomolino. 2000. Dynamic biogeography and conservation of endangered species. *Journal of Nature science*. 403(6765): 84.
- Chapin Iii, F. S., E. S. Zavaleta, V. T. Eviner , R. L. Naylor, P. M. Vitousek, H. L. Reynolds, M. C. Mack. 2000. Consequences of changing biodiversity. *Nature*. 405(6783): 234.
- Chapman, P. J., L. L. Chapman. 1982. Vincent Wildlife Trust. Otter survey of Ireland. 1980-81.
- Chughtai, M.S., M. Altaf, I. Manzoor, B. Safeer, S. Yasrub. 2018. Assessment of human and wild boar (*Sus scrofa*) conflict from district Bagh, Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Pakistan. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 2: 10-21.
- Coblentz, D. D., K. H. Riitters 2004. Topographic controls on the regional-scale biodiversity of the south-western USA. *Journal of Biogeography*. 31(7): 1125-1138.
- Connell, J. H. 1978. Diversity in tropical rain forests and coral reefs. *Science*.

- Conover, M. R., W. C. Pitt, K. K. Kessle, T. J. DuBo, W. A. Sanborn. 1995. Review of human injuries, illnesses, and economic losses caused by wildlife in the United States. *Wildlife Society Bulletin* (1973-2006). 23(3): 407-414.
- Cooper-Ellis, S., D. R. Foster, G. Carlton, A. Lezberg. 1999. Forest response to catastrophic wind: results from an experimental hurricane. *Ecology*. 80(8): 2683-2696.
- Costa-Neto, E. M., M. V. M. Oliveira. 2000. Cockroach is good for asthma: zootherapeutic practices in Northeastern Brazil. *Human Ecology Review*. 41-51.
- Cottureau, P. 1972. Les Incidences Du'Bang'Des Avions Supersoniques Sur Les Productions Et La Vie Animals. *Revue Medicine Veterinaire*. 123(11): 1367-1409.
- Dale, V. H., L. A. Joyce, S. McNulty, R. P. Neilson, M. P. Ayres, M. D. Flannigan, D. Simberloff. 2001. Climate change and forest disturbances: climate change can affect forests by altering the frequency, intensity, duration, and timing of fire, drought, introduced species, insect and pathogen outbreaks, hurricanes, windstorms, ice storms, or landslides. *AIBS Bulletin*. 51(9): 723-734.
- Davidson, A. D., M. J. Hamilton, A. G. Boyer, J. H. Brown, G. Ceballos. 2009. Multiple ecological pathways to extinction in mammals. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*. 106(26): 10702-10705.
- Del Valle, Y. G., E. J. Naranjo, J. Caballero, C. Martorell, F. Ruan-Soto, P. L. Enríquez. 2015. Cultural significance of wild mammals in mayan and mestizo communities of the Lacandon Rainforest, Chiapas, Mexico. *Journal of ethnobiology and ethnomedicine*. 11(1): 36.
- Di Giulio, M., R. Holderegger, S. Tobias. 2009. Effects of habitat and landscape fragmentation on humans and biodiversity in densely populated landscapes. *Journal of environmental management*. 90(10): 2959-2968.
- Díaz, S., A. Purvis, J. H. Cornelissen, G. M. Mace, M. J. Donoghue, R. M. Ewers, W. D. Pearse. 2013). Functional traits, the phylogeny of function, and ecosystem service vulnerability. *Ecology and evolution*. 3(9): 2958-2975.
- Díaz, S., M. Cabido. 2001. Vive la difference: plant functional diversity matters to ecosystem processes. *Trends in ecology & evolution*. 16(11): 646-655.
- Din, J. U., S. Hameed, K. A. Shah, M. A. Khan, S. Khan, M. Ali, M. A. Nawaz. 2013. Abundance of canids and human canid conflict in the Hindu Kush Mountain range of Pakistan. *Wildlife Biology in Practice*. 9(2): 20-29.
- Duffy, J. E. 2002. Biodiversity and ecosystem function: the consumer connection. *Oikos*. 99(2): 201-219.
- Farias, A. A., F. M. Jaksic. 2011. Low functional richness and redundancy of a predator assemblage in native forest fragments of Chiloe Island, Chile. *Journal of Animal Ecology*. 80(4): 809-817.
- Farias, A. A., G. L. Svensson. 2014. Ecoregional vulnerability assessment for the functional richness of South American carnivorans (Mammalia: Carnivora). *Journal of Mammalian Evolution*. 21(4): 437-450.

- Fatima, S.A., M. Altaf, S. Nazer, A.R. Abbasi. 2019. Study of anthropogenic impacts on snow leopards in district Neelum, Azad Jammu and Kashmir-Pakistan. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 3: 21-27.
- Feore, S. M. 1994. The distribution and abundance of the badger *Meles meles* L in Northern Ireland. *Irish Naturalist*. 27(1): 10-18.
- Ferreira, F. S., S. V. Brito, S. C. Ribeiro, W. O. Almeida, R. R. Alves. 2009. Zootherapeutics utilized by residents of the community Poco Dantas, Crato-CE, Brazil. *Journal of Ethnobiology and Ethnomedicine*. 5(1): 21.
- Frazier, J. 2007. Sustainable use of wildlife: The view from archaeozoology. *Journal for Nature Conservation*. 15(3): 163-173.
- Freddy, D. J., W. M. Bronaugh, M. C. Fowler. 1986. Responses of mule deer to disturbance by persons afoot and snowmobiles. *Wildlife Society Bulletin (1973-2006)*. 14(1): 63-68.
- Garcia-Solache, M. A., A. Casadevall. 2010. Global warming will bring new fungal diseases for mammals. *MBio*. 1(1): e00061-10.
- González-Maya, J. F., L. R. Viquez-R., A. Arias-Alzate, J. L. Belant, G. Ceballos. 2016. Spatial patterns of species richness and functional diversity in Costa Rican terrestrial mammals: implications for conservation. *Diversity and Distributions*. 22(1): 43-56.
- Grime, J. P. 1973. Competitive exclusion in herbaceous vegetation. *Nature*. 242(5396): 344.
- Hanazaki, N., R. R. Alves, A. Begossi. 2009. Hunting and use of terrestrial fauna used by Caiçaras from the Atlantic Forest coast (Brazil). *Journal of Ethnobiology and Ethnomedicine*. 5(1): 36.
- Happold, D. C. D. 1995. The interactions between humans and mammals in Africa in relation to conservation: a review. *Biodiversity & Conservation*. 4(4): 395-414.
- Harris, L. K., R. H. Gimblett, W. W. Shaw. 1995. Multiple use management: using a GIS model to understand conflicts between recreationists and sensitive wildlife. *Society & Natural Resources*. 8(6): 559-572.
- Harris, L. K., W. W. Shaw, J. Schelhas. 1997. Urban neighbors' wildlife-related attitudes and behaviors near federally protected areas in Tucson, Arizona, USA. *Natural Areas Journal*. 17(2): 144-148.
- Harris, S., G. C. Smith. 1987. Demography of two urban fox (*Vulpes vulpes*) populations. *Journal of Applied Ecology*. 75-86.
- Hausner, V. H., N. G. Yoccoz, R. A. Ims. 2003. Selecting indicator traits for monitoring land use impacts: birds in northern coastal birch forests. *Ecological Applications*. 13(4): 999-1012.
- Heikinheimo, H., M. Fortelius, J. Eronen, H. Mannila. 2007. Biogeography of European land mammals shows environmentally distinct and spatially coherent clusters. *Journal of Biogeography*. 34(6): 1053-1064.
- Heine, J. C., T. W. Speir. 1989. Ornithogenic soils of the Cape Bird Adelie penguin rookeries, Antarctica. *Polar Biology*. 10(2): 89-99.
- Henle, K., D. Alard, J. Clitherow, P. Cobb, L. Firbank, T. Kull, D. Wascher. 2008. Identifying and managing the conflicts between agriculture and biodiversity conservation in Europe—A review. *Agriculture, Ecosystems and Environment*. 124(1-2): 60-71.

- Hillebrand, H., B. Matthiessen. 2009. Biodiversity in a complex world: consolidation and progress in functional biodiversity research. *Ecology letters*. 12(12): 1405-1419.
- Holt, R. D., M. Barfield. 2009. Trophic interactions and range limits: the diverse roles of predation. *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London B: Biological Sciences*. 276(1661): 1435-1442.
- Holt, R. D., T. H. Keitt, M. A. Lewis, B. A. Maurer, M. L. Taper. 2005. Theoretical models of species' borders: single species approaches. *Oikos*. 108(1): 18-27.
- Holway, D. A., A. V. Suarez. 2006. Homogenization of ant communities in mediterranean California: the effects of urbanization and invasion. *Biological conservation*. 127(3): 319-326.
- Hood, G. A., K. L. Parker. 2001. Impact of human activities on grizzly bear habitat in Jasper National Park. *Wildlife Society Bulletin*. 624-638.
- Hovelsrud-Broda, G. K. 1999. The integrative role of seals in an east Greenlandic hunting village. *Arctic anthropology*. 37-50.
- Huntington, H. P. 1992. The Alaska Eskimo Whaling Commission and other cooperative marine mammal management organizations in northern Alaska. *Polar Record*. 28(165): 119-126.
- Huston, M. 1979. A general hypothesis of species diversity. *The American Naturalist*. 113(1): 81-101
- Ijaz, S., S. Adil, H. Aslam, R. Kanwal, S. Afsheen. 2020. Human interaction, conflict, threats and role of mammals-A review. *Journal of Ethnomedicine and Ethnoecology*. 1: 1-11.
- Ijaz, S., S. Adil, H. Aslam, R. Kanwal, S. Afsheen. 2020. Human interaction, conflict, threats and role of mammals-A review. *Journal of Ethnomedicine and Ethnoecology*. 1: 1-11.
- Ijaz, S., S. Adil. 2021. Anthropogenic impacts on the distribution of mammalian species in the vicinity of Head Trimmu, Punjab, Pakistan. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 5: 168-175.
- Inserro, J. C. 1997. States, agencies discuss solutions for handling Yellowstone bison, brucellosis. *Journal of the American Veterinary Medical Association*. 210(5): 593.
- IUCN. . 2001. Species Survival Commission, International Union for Conservation of Nature, & Natural Resources. Species Survival Commission, IUCN Red List categories and criteria. 2(1): 236.
- IUCN. 2003. Guidelines for application of IUCN Red List criteria at regional levels. Switzerland and Cambridge,UK. 61(32): 23-56.
- IUCN. 2008. Guidelines for Using the IUCN Red List Categories and Criteria. Survival Commission. Switzerland and Cambridge,UK. 7(2): 115-156.
- Jahangeer, M., R.A. Minhas, S. Awan. 2019. Current distribution and status of Himalayan Grey Langur (*Semnopithecus ajax*) in Lachhrat forest Range, Azad Jammu and Kashmir-Pakistan. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 3: 20-30.
- Kamanga, P., P. Vedeld, E. Sjaastad. 2009. Forest incomes and rural livelihoods in Chiradzulu District, Malawi. *Ecological Economics*. 68(3): 613-624.
- Kanda, L. L., T. K. Fuller, P. R. Sievert, R. L. Kellogg. 2009. Seasonal source-sink dynamics at the edge of a species' range. *Ecology*. 90(6): 1574-1585.
- Kanwal, R., S. Adil, H. Aslam, S. Ijaz, S. Afsheen. 2019. Human impacts and interaction with mammalian species-A review. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 3: 13-26.

- Kanwal, R., S. Adil, H. Aslam, S. Ijaz, S. Afsheen. 2019. Human impacts and interaction with mammalian species-A review. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 3: 13-26.
- King, M. M., G. W. Workman,. 1986. Response of desert bighorn sheep to human harassment: management implications. In *Transactions of the North American Wildlife and Natural Resources Conference*. Vol. 51: 74-85.
- Koster, J. M. 2008. Hunting with dogs in Nicaragua: an optimal foraging approach. *Current Anthropology*. 49(5): 935-944.
- Kuss, F. R., A. R. Graefe, J. J. Vaske. 1990. Visitor impact management: A review of research. Volume. 1: 187-217.
- Lamhna, E. N. 1979. Provisional distribution atlas of amphibians, reptiles and mammals in Ireland. *Journal of Science*. 34(2): 44-67.
- Lavorel, S., É. Garnier. 2002. Predicting changes in community composition and ecosystem functioning from plant traits: revisiting the Holy Grail. *Functional ecology*. 16(5): 545-556.
- Lawton, J. H. 1993 Range, population abundance and conservation. *Trends Ecol. Evo*. 18: 409–413.
- Le Saout, S., M. Hoffmann, Y. Shi, A. Hughes, C. Bernard, T. M. Brooks, A. S. Rodrigues. 2013. Protected areas and effective biodiversity conservation. *Science*. 342(6160): 803-805.
- Lees, A. C., N. G Moura, A. Santana, A. Aleixo, J. Barlow, E. Berenguer, T. A. Gardner. 2012. Paragominas: a quantitative baseline inventory of an eastern Amazonian avifauna. *Revista Brasileira de Ornitologia*. 20(2): 93-118.
- Lev, E. 2003. Traditional healing with animals (zootherapy): medieval to present-day Levantine practice. *Journal of Ethnopharmacolog*. 85(1): 107-118.
- Levin, S. A. 2005. Self-organization and the emergence of complexity in ecological systems. *AIBS Bulletin*. 55(12): 1075-1079.
- Lohani, U. 2010. Man-animal relationships in Central Nepal. *Journal of ethnobiology and ethnomedicine*. 6(1): 31.
- Londoño-Betancourth, J. C. 2009. Valoración cultural del uso e importancia de la fauna silvestre en cautividad en tres barrios de Pereira (Risaralda). *Bol Cient Mus Hist Nat*. 13(1): 33-46.
- Luck, G. W., S. Lavorel, S. McIntyre, K. Lumb. 2012. Improving the application of vertebrate trait-based frameworks to the study of ecosystem services. *Journal of Animal Ecology*. 81(5): 1065-1076.
- Lugo, A. E. 2008. Visible and invisible effects of hurricanes on forest ecosystems: an international review. *Austral Ecology*. 33(4): 368-398.
- MacKinney, LC. 1946. Animal substances in materia medica. *J. Hist. Med. Allied Sci*. 1(1).
- Magige, F. J., T. Holmern, S. Stokke, C. Mlingwa, E. Røskaft. 2009. Does illegal hunting affect density and behaviour of African grassland birds? A case study on ostrich (*Struthio camelus*). *Biodiversity and conservation*. 18(5): 1361-1373.
- Mahawar, M. M., D. P. Jaroli. 2008. Traditional zootherapeutic studies in India: a review. *Journal of Ethnobiology and Ethnomedicine*. 4(1): 17.
- Manzoor, I., M. Altaf, B. Safeer, S. Yasrub. 2018. Study of diversity, distribution and cultural uses of house mouse (*Mus musculus*) in district Bagh, Azad Jammu and Kashmir-Pakistan. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 2: 22-29.

- Marques, J. G. 1997. Fauna medicinal: Recurso do ambiente ou ameaça à biodiversidade. *Mutum.* 1(1): 4.
- Mattson, D. J., R. R. Knight, B. M. Blanchard. 1987. The effects of developments and primary roads on grizzly bear habitat use in Yellowstone National Park, Wyoming. *Bears: Their Biology and Management.* 259-273.
- Mbwambo, Z. H., R. L. A. Mahunnah, E. J. Kayombo. 2007. Traditional health practitioner and the scientist: bridging the gap in contemporary health research in Tanzania. *Tanzania Journal of Health Research* 9(2): 115-120.
- Milton, K. 2003. The critical role played by animal source foods in human (Homo) evolution. *The Journal of nutrition.* 133(11): 3886S-3892S.
- Mols, C. M., M. E. Visser. 2007. Great tits (*Parus major*) reduce caterpillar damage in commercial apple orchards. *PLoS One.* 2(2): e202.
- Monnet, A. C., F. Jiguet, C. N. Meynard, D. Mouillot, N. Mouquet, W. Thuiller, V. Devictor. 2014. Asynchrony of taxonomic, functional and phylogenetic diversity in birds. *Global Ecology and Biogeography.* 23(7): 780-788.
- Monteiro, J. M., U. P. de Albuquerque, E. M. de Freitas Lins-Neto, E. L. de Araújo, E. L. C. de Amorim. 2006. Use patterns and knowledge of medicinal species among two rural communities in Brazil's semi-arid northeastern region. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology.* 105(1-2): 173-186.
- Mootosamy, A., M. F. Mahomoodally. 2014. A quantitative ethnozoological assessment of traditionally used animal-based therapies in the tropical island of Mauritius. *Journal of ethnopharmacology.* 154(3): 847-857.
- Musiega, D. E., S. N. Kazadi. 2004. Simulating the East African wildebeest migration patterns using GIS and remote sensing. *African Journal of Ecology.* 42(4): 355-362.
- Myers, J. H., S. D. Imberloff, A. M. Kuris, J. R. Carey. 2000. Eradication revisited: dealing with exotic species. *Trends in ecology and evolution.* 15(8): 316-320.
- Myers, N. 1990. The biodiversity challenge: expanded hot-spots analysis. *Environmentalist* 10(4): 243-256.
- Newton, I. 2004. The recent declines of farmland bird populations in Britain: an appraisal of causal factors and conservation actions. *Ibis.* 146(4): 579-600.
- Ogutu, J. O., N. Owen-Smith. 2003. ENSO, rainfall and temperature influences on extreme population declines among African savanna ungulates. *Ecology Letters.* 6(5): 412-419.
- Pattiselanno, F. 2004, April. Wildlife utilization and food security in West Papua, Indonesia. In *SEARCA Agriculture and Development Seminar Series, SEARCA Los Baños.* Vol. 13.
- Peters, C. M., A. H. Gentry, R. O. Mendelsohn. 1989. Valuation of an Amazonian rainforest. *Nature.* 339(6227): 655.
- Pimentel, D., B. Berger, D. Filiberto, M. Newton, B. Wolfe, E. Karabinakis, ... S. Nandagopal. 2004. Water resources: agricultural and environmental issues. *BioScience.* 54(10): 909-918.
- Pimm, S. L., G. J. Russell, J. L. Gittleman, T. M. Brooks. 1995. The future of biodiversity. *Science.* 269(5222): 347-350.

- Pinto, M. F., J. R. F. Silva, R. R. N. Alves, A. K. Nishida. 2010. Os animais do manguezal do estuário do Rio Jaguaribe, Aracati, Ceará-Uma abordagem etnozoológica. *A Etnozoologia no Brasil: Importância, Status atual e Perspectivas*. Volume, 7(1).
- Purtauf, T., I. Roschewitz, J. Dauber, C. Thies, T. Tschardtke, V. Wolters. 2005. The critical role played by animal source foods in human (Homo) evolution. *The Journal of nutrition*. 133(11): 3886-3892.
- Purvis, A., J. L. Gittleman, T. Brooks. (Eds.). 2005. *Phylogeny and conservation*. Cambridge University Press. www.cambridge.org/9780521825024.
- Rasheed, S., M. Bashir, A. Jaddon. 2020. Diversity and status of mammalian fauna of Abbaspur, Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Pakistan. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 4: 85-93.
- Rasheed, S., M. Bashir, A. Jaddon. 2020. Diversity and status of mammalian fauna of Abbaspur, Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Pakistan. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 4: 85-93.
- Redford, K. H. 1992. The empty forest. *BioScience*. 42(6): 412-422.
- Regan, H. M., R. Lupia, A. N. Drinnan, M. A. Burgman. 2001. The currency and tempo of extinction. *The American Naturalist*. 157(1): 1-10.
- Reid, N., R. A. McDONALD, W. I. Montgomery. 2007. Mammals and agri-environment schemes: hare haven or pest paradise?. *Journal of Applied Ecology*. 44(6): 1200-1208.
- Riaz, T., M. Altaf. 2021. Diversity and cultural uses of mammals in Dhirkot, Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Pakistan. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 5: 159-167.
- Riley, S. J., D. J. Decker, 2000. Wildlife stakeholder acceptance capacity for cougars in Montana. *Wildlife Society Bulletin*. 931-939.
- Ripple, W. J., R. L. Beschta. 2004. Wolves and the ecology of fear: can predation risk structure ecosystems?. *AIBS Bulletin*. 54(8): 755-766.
- Roberts, T. J. 2005. *Field guide to the large and medium-sized mammals of Pakistan*. Oxford University Press. 12(6): 214.
- Roedenbeck, I. A., L. Fahrig, C. S. Findlay, J. E. Houlahan, J. A. Jaeger, N. Klar, E. A. Van der Grift. 2007. The Rauschholzhausen agenda for road ecology. *Ecology and society*. 12(1).
- Romin, L. A., J. A. Bissonette. 1996. Deer: vehicle collisions: status of state monitoring activities and mitigation efforts. *Wildlife Society Bulletin*. 276-283.
- Rondinini, C., M. Di Marco, F. Chiozza, G. Santulli, D. Baisero, P. Visconti, G. Amori. 2011. Global habitat suitability models of terrestrial mammals. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London B: Biological Sciences*. 366(1578): 2633-2641.
- Rosegrant, M. 2000. *Transforming the rural Asian economy: The unfinished revolution*. Asian Development Bank. Vol. 1.
- Ruan-Soto, F., J. Caballero, C. Martorell, J. Cifuentes, A. R. González-Esquinca, R. Garibay-Orijel. 2013. Evaluation of the degree of mycophilia-mycophobia among highland and lowland inhabitants from Chiapas, Mexico. *Journal of ethnobiology and ethnomedicine*. 9(1): 36.
- Ruegg, K. C., R. J. Hijmans, C. Moritz. 2006. Climate change and the origin of migratory pathways in the Swainson's thrush, *Catharus ustulatus*. *Journal of Biogeography*. 33(7): 1172-1182.
- Saba, M., A. Hamza, M. Hussain, S. Yousaf. 2020. Biodegradation of plastics and its impact on environmental pollution-a review. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 4: 109-119.

- Safeer, B., Z. Rasheed, M. Altaf, I. Manzoor, S. Yasrub. 2018. Assessment of human-Indian crested porcupine (*Hystrix indica*) conflict in district Bagh, Azad Jammu and Kashmir. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 2: 1-12.
- Saino, N., R. Ambrosini, D. Rubolini, J. von Hardenberg, A. Provenzale, K. Hüppop, M. Romano. 2011. Climate warming, ecological mismatch at arrival and population decline in migratory birds. *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London: Biological Sciences*. 278(1707): 835-842.
- Saleem, R., M. Altaf, M. Umair, M.S. Amjad, A.M. Abbasi. 2021. Ethnopharmacological applications of the amphibians and reptiles among the people in the vicinity of Margalla Hill National Park, Islamabad, Pakistan. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 5: 13-25.
- Sánchez-Cuervo, A. M., T. M. Aide, M. L. Clark, A. Etter. 2012. Land cover change in Colombia: surprising forest recovery trends between 2001 and 2010. *PloS one*. 7(8): e43943.
- Schipper, J., J. S. Chanson, F. Chiozza, N. A. Cox, M. Hoffmann, V. Katariya, J. Baillie. 2008. The status of the world's land and marine mammals: diversity, threat, and knowledge. *Science* 322(5899): 225-230.
- Schwartz, S. H. 2006. A theory of cultural value orientations: Explication and applications. *Comparative sociology*. 5(2): 137-182.
- Sechrest, W., T. M. Brooks, G. A. da Fonseca, W. R. Konstant, R. A. Mittermeier, A. Purvis, J. L. Gittleman. 2002. Hotspots and the conservation of evolutionary history. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*. 99(4): 2067-2071.
- Şekercioğlu, Ç. H., G. C. Daily, P. R. Ehrlich. 2004. Ecosystem consequences of bird declines. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*. 101(52):18042-18047.
- Şekercioğlu, Ç. H., R. B. Primack, J. Wormworth. 2012. The effects of climate change on tropical birds. *Biological Conservation*. 148(1): 1-18.
- Sekhar, N. U. 1998. Crop and livestock depredation caused by wild animals in protected areas: the case of Sariska Tiger Reserve, Rajasthan, India. *Environmental Conservation*. 25(2): 160-171.
- Sidra, S., R. Saleem, S. Ghafoor, H. Azeem, I. Imtiaz, Z. Parveen. 2019. Fecal matter as a bio-indicator tool for heavy metal pollution. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 3: 1-7.
- Silva, F. D. S., M. A. Ramos, N. Hanazaki, U. P. D. Albuquerque. 2011. Dynamics of traditional knowledge of medicinal plants in a rural community in the Brazilian semi-arid region. *Revista Brasileira de Farmacognosia*. 21(3): 382-391.
- Simpson, G. G. 1964. Species density of North American recent mammals. *Systematic zoology*. 13(2): 57-73.
- Sparks, T. H., A. Menzel. 2002. Observed changes in seasons: an overview. *International Journal of Climatology*. 22(14): 1715-1725.
- Spencer, R. J., V. C. Cavanough, G. S. Baxter, M. S. Kennedy. 2005. Adult free zones in small mammal populations: response of Australian native rodents to reduced cover. *Austral Ecology*. 30(8): 868-876.
- Steffen, W., Å. Persson, L. Deutsch, J. Zalasiewicz, M. Williams, K. Richardson, M. Molina. 2011. The Anthropocene: From global change to planetary stewardship. *Ambio*. 40(7): 739.

- Stoate, C., A. Báldi, P. Beja, N. D. Boatman, I. Herzon, A. Van Doorn, C. Ramwell. 2009. Ecological impacts of early 21st century agricultural change in Europe—a review. *Journal of environmental management*. 91(1): 22-46.
- Studsrød, J. E., P. Wegge. 1995. Park-people relationships: the case of damage caused by park animals around the Royal Bardia National Park, Nepal. *Environmental conservation*. 22(2): 133-142.
- Tilman, D., C. L. Lehman, K. T. Thomson. 1997. Plant diversity and ecosystem productivity: theoretical considerations. *Proceedings of the national academy of sciences*. 94(5): 1857-1861.
- Umair, M. 2018. Anthropogenic impacts on the coastal wetland and wildlife-A review. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 2: 30-36.
- Umair, M., D. Sinha, M. Haasan. 2022. Ethnopharmacological uses of animals and plants in cancer treatment-a review. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 2: 32-47.
- Uraguchi, K., K. Yamamura, T. Saitoh. 2009. Estimating number of families for an urban fox population by using two public data sets. *Population ecology*. 51(2): 271-277.
- Vijayakumar, S., S. Prabhu, J. M. Yabesh, R. Pragashraj. 2015. A quantitative ethnozoological study of traditionally used animals in Pachamalai hills of Tamil Nadu, India. *Journal of ethnopharmacology*. 171: 51-63.
- Vitousek, P. M., H. A. Mooney, J. Lubchenco, J. M. Melillo. 1997. Human domination of Earth's ecosystems. *Science*. 277(5325): 494-499.
- Weaver, J. L., P. C. Paquet, L. F. Ruggiero. 1996. Resilience and conservation of large carnivores in the Rocky Mountains. *Conservation Biology*. 10(4): 964-976.
- Weiss, H. B. 1947. Entomological medicaments of the past. *Journal of the New York Entomological Society*. 55(2): 155-168.
- Westerberg, L., Ö. Östman, U. Wennergren. 2005. Movement effects on equilibrium distributions of habitat generalists in heterogeneous landscapes. *Ecological Modelling*. 188(2-4): 432-447.
- Yost, A. C., R. G. Wright. 2001. Moose, caribou, and grizzly bear distribution in relation to road traffic in Denali National Park, Alaska. *Arctic*. 41-48.
- Younus, S., S. Nazer, M. Altaf, I. Manzoor, B. Safeer, S. Yasrub. 2018. Study of human and Asiatic Jackal (*Canis aureus*) conflict from Bagh district, Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Pakistan. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 2: 1-10.